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“MY BELOVED”

Mama and Papa, my guide,
In all endeavors, you are the reason,
Your love, irreplaceable,
Without equal, without measure, without end.

Mama Marlyn, your care,
Warm touch, full of love,
In every night that I weaken,
Your smiles are what strengthen me.

Papa Cecilo, my pillar,
In hardship and pain, you are my support,
In your hands full of effort,
You enriched our lives.

Thank you for your unwavering love,
For the sacrifices without regret,
No words can compare to your kindness,
For you are my life, my treasure.

Until eternity,
I will not forget your kindness,
Mama Marlyn and Papa Cecilo,
Here in my heart, you are still number one!